

IRANIAN TEACHERS AND STUDENTS' ATTITUDES ON TRANSLANGUAGING IN EAP AND EGP CLASSROOMS

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Abstract

Translanguaging is a very recent and significant approach to teaching English that speeds up the learning process. In order to further the research on how beneficial translanguaging may be for both students and teachers when teaching English, there has been a rising interest in investigating various elements of mother tongue usage during English classes in recent years. Despite all current research worldwide, the majority of Iranian students and instructors still do not favor this approach, and many think that it has more drawbacks than advantages. It is believed that using this technique incorrectly can hinder learning process rather than enhancing it. As a result, more research—which hasn't been done much in Iran—is required to compare EAP and EGP classes while using translanguaging in EFL classrooms, as well as students' and teachers' attitudes toward this topic. In order to assess the effectiveness of students' comprehension in both EAP and EGP classrooms, this study will look into instructors' and students' attitudes on translanguaging. This study looked at how Iranian instructors and students felt about translanguaging, the connection between speaking one's native language and learning efficiency, and comparisons of EAP and EGP classrooms. For this purpose, four instructors were interviewed and a total of four courses, including two EAP and two EGP classrooms, were observed. Participants in this study were also given questionnaires in person and online. The study may provide further information on the value of translation and how it affects the standard of instruction. The findings of this study have significant implications for educators, pedagogues, and decision-makers working in multilingual settings, as well as providing a starting point for further investigation into the application and effectiveness of translanguaging approaches.

Keywords: Translanguaging, Code Switching, EAP Classroom, EGP Classroom, Teachers' Attitude, Students' Attitude.

1. INTRODUCTION

A brief introduction to translanguaging and a few definitions provided by academics make up the first chapter. Following a brief discussion of the vacuum left by other investigations, the study's purpose and method are laid forth. The relevance of this study is also discussed and expounded upon. The written research questions and related hypothesis are presented. The definitions of the study's important terms are provided at the conclusion of this chapter for your convenience.

Here, translanguaging is regarded as a subfield of TEFL and translanguaging pedagogies as tools for challenging the ideology of monolingualism and monoglossia in schools. It is a fresh topic that many researchers are interested in studying. Particularly with relation to Iran. It appears that English language education has undergone more than a "multimodal" shift in recent years. From the early debate challenging the distinction between native and non-native

speakers of English (Liu, 1999) and the development of World English (Kachru B. B., 1992) to the more recent acceleration of Global English language teaching (Rose & Galloway, 2019) and multimodal and translanguaging as a theory, method, or approach of language education (García & Li, 2014; Li, 2022; Li & García, 2022), it seems that English language education has witnessed more than a ‘multilingual turn’ (May, 2013); it is going through a critical ‘trans-era’ that recognizes both linguistic and cultural diversity, and views social, cultural, and multimodal resources as valuable assets in learning for inclusive education (Dovchin & Lee, 2019).

However, there have been just a few studies on the EFL curriculum in Iranian educational system that teaches English for Academic Purpose (EAP) and English for General Purpose (EGP) (Khonamri, F. et al., 2022; Namaziandost, E. et al., 2019; Mirbazel, SK. & Arjmandi, M., 2018). Translanguaging is still a challenging area in Iranian ELT classes, and many families and students themselves are still hesitant to learn about it. A small amount of research on translanguaging in EAP classrooms were conducted (Hiller, K. E., 2021)) as well as EGP classrooms (Llanes, À., & Cots, J. M., 2022)), however there have been very few studies on translanguaging in EAP and EGP classrooms in Iran..

As a result, this study intends to look at how instructors and students perceive about using L1 in EAP and EGP classes, as well as examine how L1 usage affects reading in such settings.

Although code switching, also known as translanguaging, is now regarded as a great EFL technique in bilingual and multilingual classrooms (Elashhab, S., 2020; Ticheloven, A., et al., 2021; Galante A., 2020), there is still a problem with teachers' generally unfavourable attitudes toward the use of L1s for teaching English in EAP and EGP settings. This leads to a dearth of research on the effects of L1 usage in EGP and EAP classes and how it affects reading ability. Teachers' expectations have an ongoing impact on their pupils and can be a significant burden for those learning English.

The classroom environment and students' L2 learning are both significantly influenced by the attitude of the teachers. The teacher is a key player in the classroom, and the way they educate largely depends on their attitudes. This very unfavorable perception of translanguaging leads to the use of rather conventional procedures in both EAP and EGP classes. According to Aminifard Y. and Mehrpour, S. (2019) teachers would still choose to take their time and educate students using just English, even if teaching English at lower levels would be more difficult and time-consuming without L1 usage. It is important to note that the teaching approach must be approved by the students that show up to class, thus it is important to consider how the students feel about it. It is important to note that the teaching approach must be approved by the students that show up to class, thus it is important to consider how the students feel about it. The teaching approach is expected to be accepted by the students in order for them to pay attention and for the learning process to go smoothly. Therefore, it is crucial to recognize that students' attitudes are not unimportant.

Thus, this study's goal is to close this gap and examine how instructors and students perceive the usage of translanguaging in EAP and EGP classes while also examining the effects it has on their reading ability.

Translanguaging significantly affects how effectively students learn. As a result, this study analyses Iranian instructors' and students' attitudes on translanguaging as well as the use of L1 in both EAP and EGP classes in Iran. It also offers some empirical data on the degree of L1 usage in both Iranian EAP and EGP classrooms. This study offers a comprehensive understanding of translanguaging in Iranian EFL classrooms and its impacts within the Iranian setting. The Iranian setting, a non-native English-speaking nation, greatly benefits from this study.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Using the translanguaging method, non-native English-speaking countries, particularly those in Asia, had positive outcomes. Recent changes in EFL education in non-native English-speaking countries were made as a result of this strategy, which have had a profound impact on how instructors and students both regard learning English as a foreign language. The word "code switching" was initially used in the early 20th century, although sociolinguist Einar Haugen first used it in 1954. In reaction to the transatlantic slave trade, black groups had to create their own traditions, ethnicities, and languages. Assimilation into the black community or acting on a survival impulse are what code switching is similar to.

The importance of code switching is brought forth in two key ways. First, the distinctions between Standard English and ASL, as well as between Black American Sign Language (BASL) and African-American Vernacular English (AAVE) (BASL). The disregard for the languages and dialects of the black people follows. In order to preserve overall performance, communities of color now rely on code switching. Later, the term "translanguaging" was used to describe the process of modifying the script.

According to Garcia O. (2009) The process through which bilingual or multilingual speakers employ their language repertoires as an integrated communication system is referred to as translanguaging, In order to optimize their communication potential, bilinguals "use multiple language traits or modes." The act of employing different languages interchangeably to overcome linguistic barriers, effectively communicate ideas in speech or writing, and eventually accomplish successful communication is another definition for translanguaging (Csillik & Golubeva, 2019).

Until roughly 20 years ago, translanguaging, usually referred to as code switching, was rarely employed in EFL educational institutions. Ogame (1997) explored code switching and its relationship with discourse studies on 5 females Japanese EFL learners in one of his earlier research projects. According to Ogame (1997) The subjects may use interjections, adjective, adverb, noun, and sentence switches to communicate their particular sentiments and affirm their unity (p. 122).

Additionally, this code switching may be categorized as discourse-related, according to Martin-Jones (1995). Later, Edmondson, W. (2004) described code switching as "world-switching," or the changeover from one form of discourse to another, in separate research. It may not necessarily follow that teachers' preferred behavior will be the most conducive to learning and

that teaching in a language other than the target language should be encouraged, even though "25 years of study showed that EFL learners rather and expect corrective treatment of their linguistic output" that showed "the preference of learners to be unambiguous and explicit correction" (P.174).

In research conducted in 2010, Hobbs, V. et al. found the cultural impacts that native and non-native language teachers had on code switching. Teachers who are natural speakers of the target language also use it far less frequently than non-native teachers.

The social and pedagogical elements of code switching were studied by Cahyani, H. et al. (2018). They noticed that instructors in bilingual classes utilised this strategy to "integrate the two languages in order to promote greater communication and participation in learning."

The results of a study on code switching in an EAP classroom in China by Knowles, L. R. (2019) indicated how task, ability, and interlocutor impact L1 usage. There were certain tasks or linguistic procedures that were completed fully in Chinese. Additionally, it demonstrated that children changed their codes more frequently than was predicted. It is uncommon for specialist study to explore the relationship between EGP classrooms and translanguaging or script change.

A second research of EAP university courses in China was carried out by Hiller, K. E. (2021). By analysing the results of student observation and feedback, this study proved that "translanguaging writing assignments have the potential to contribute to students' cultural knowledge, writing and communication skills, intercultural communication and awareness, and identity construction as translingual and transnational students."

One of the most recent studies on translanguaging in China is published by Siegel, J. (2022). This research was conducted on a Chinese college EAP course. The findings revealed that there was a relationship between how instructors perceived translanguaging pedagogy and how it was put into practice. Therefore, it is essential to give educators ample assistance while establishing translanguaging instruction or before adopting EAP in order to aid in their understanding of the underlying ideas and concepts.

There has been a few research on code switching and translanguaging in the context of Iran. According to research by Jamshidi, A. and Navehebrahim, M. (2013) on the usage of code switching in EFL courses, students who speak Persian are more comfortable and competent in the setting. From beginning to advanced levels, every participant in this study spoke Persian as their first language and English as their second language.

One of the most recent studies was carried out by Vosoughi, M. et al. in 2019. According to the study's findings, ELT teachers all over the world adhered to "collaborative practises," but psychological differences between content and language teachers made it more likely that this would occur, along with other problems with the country's educational institutions. They made it clear that language professors in the country were not regarded as dependable colleagues in such courses owing to their lack of experience. Outside the borders, the situation was far better, and subject and language instructors cooperated well.

Another similar study carried out on the value of L1 usage as a scaffold or a debilitating crutch for young learners was conducted by Aminifard, Y. and Mehrpour, S. (2019). The study's results revealed that educators extensively resorted to Persian for purposes other than grading students. They came to the conclusion that teachers should provide sufficient of L2 input to younger students in order to help them develop appropriate multilingual identities. According to the findings of this study, young language learners should use L1 with care.

A study on teachers' and students' attitudes about code-switching in English language instruction in Iranian EFL classrooms was done by Nazeri, S. et al. in 2021. This study discovered that students' opinions of different aspects of code switching were largely favourable. More than half of the teachers thought that code switching helped students' English and that they did not entirely rely on it for greater understanding. The teachers' opinions about code switching were unaffected by the difficulty of the course they were teaching.

Research on the perceived roles of university teachers' code-switching techniques in undergraduate English major content versus language classes was undertaken by Eslami, M., & Talebzadeh, H. (2022). According to the findings of their study, code-switching was regarded as a goal-directed technique that was far more common in topic classes. Code switching as a teaching technique, they stressed, may assist instructors in reducing the cognitive and affective burden on learners while boosting understanding and learning.

3. METHOD

Design of the Study

In the current research, in accordance with the research topic, a mixed method is used, which includes qualitative and quantitative methods. In this context, teachers' attitude towards translanguaging is investigated in a qualitative method and reading skills are evaluated in both EAP and EGP classes. In the following, the attitude of students towards translanguaging is investigated in a quantitative analysis.

Quantitative Study Section

Quantitative sections are presented in detail with explanations of each in separate sections to provide sufficient details for the research. The main goal in the quantitative part is to answer the second goal of the research "Evaluation of students' attitude towards the use of translanguaging method in EAP and EGP classes".

Statistical Population and Sample

The statistical population is said to be all the people who have common characteristics in certain aspects related to the viewpoints of the research and are subject to the desired research results. Before starting the research, the researcher should define and clarify the framework of the statistical population of that research so that both his task is clear and he can easily introduce it to others. The statistical population is also called the target population (Farhangi & SafarZadeh, 2012). The current research population includes all undergraduate and graduate female students who attend EAP and EGP classes. TEFL students attend two EAP classes and

management and architecture students attend two EGP classes. In one of the EAP classes, the focus is on reading and vocabulary skills, and in the other class, on grammar skills.

Four different classrooms (two EGP classes and two EAP classes) are the subjects of this research. Research course was held at Irshad non-profit university of Damavand. Students of this university are selected and registered through entrance exam. All the data of this research were collected during the spring 2023 academic semester.

Research Tool

In a small part, the questionnaire tool was used in the research. Questionnaire is one of the common research tools and a direct method to obtain research data. Questionnaire is a set of questions (items) that the respondent provides the necessary answer by considering them. This answer forms the data required by the researcher. Most of the questionnaires contain materials that are prepared and compiled in order to measure the dependent and independent variables and the required characteristics (Farhangi & SafarZadeh, 2012).

First, the questionnaire was distributed online among 123 students in order to investigate their attitude towards translanguaging in different ways, which are described in detail in the questionnaire. 60 other students answered the questionnaire in person. Therefore, in total, the questionnaire was distributed among 183 undergraduate and graduate students. This questionnaire is derived from two questionnaires: Moody et al. (2019) & Nambisan (2014). By answering the questionnaire based on a 5-point Likert scale, the students show how much they agree or disagree with the claims made in the questionnaire (quite disagree, agree, neutral, agree, quite agree).

The questionnaire of this research, an example of which is given in the appendix section, includes two parts: individual questions and specialized questions. Individual questions include age, field and level of education, level of English language and familiarity with other languages, and specialized questions that consist of 23 questions and are about the students' opinions about the general methods of translanguaging.

Data Collection Method

At first, the questionnaire was distributed online among 123 students in order to investigate their attitude towards translanguaging in different ways, which are described in detail in the questionnaire. 60 other students answered the questionnaire in person. Therefore, in total, the questionnaire was distributed among 183 undergraduate and graduate students. This questionnaire is taken from two questionnaires Moody et al (2019) & Nambisan (2014). By answering the questionnaire based on a 5-point Likert scale, the students show how much they agree or disagree with the claims made in the questionnaire (quite disagree, disagree, neutral, agree, quite agree).

Data Analysis

After collecting the necessary data using the data collection tool which is the questionnaire, these data should be analyzed. The obtained data are analyzed by examining the average of the research questions in EAP and EGP classes and examining the percentage of people who agree

and disagree in the two classes. The results obtained from these analyzes finally show the attitude of the students towards the translanguaging in these two classes. Next, Cronbach's alpha test is performed to check the reliability of the questionnaire questions. The value of Cronbach's alpha shows the correlation of the questions of a questionnaire. In the following, the t-test is performed with the aim of checking the averages in two classes, EAP and EGP. Parametric tests such as t-test are used when the variance of the samples is equal or almost equal. Secondly, the data should be at the distance and relative measurement level. Thirdly, the data distribution in the society should be normal or close to normal. In this study, all three conditions of using t-test are fulfilled. In the t-test, the average of both EAP and EGP classes is compared with the assumed average which is equal to 3 in this study.

Exploratory factor analysis is also one of the other tests performed in the quantitative section. The factor analysis method can be used as a tool to discover the possible amount of data reduction, which is called exploratory factor analysis. In the current research, exploratory factor analysis has been used means that grouping variables that have internal correlation. Often this analysis is done in the early stages of the research. Other goals of exploratory factor analysis are tool as well as theory construction. All the mentioned tests have been done with the help of statistical software SPSS version 26.

4. ANALYSIS

4.1 Descriptive Statistics Section

4.1.1 Demographic

In this section, the demographic characteristics of the studied sample have been described in terms of gender, education, age, English language level and familiarity with other languages in the form of statistical tables and graphs.

4.1.1.1 Gender

All the participants in the research are women from my country.

4.1.1.2 Age

Table 4-1 shows the status of the studied sample in terms of age variable and according to the observed frequency, the age group of 20 to 25 years with a frequency of 68.9% is more than other age groups.

Table 4.1: Sample distribution by age

	Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Age	Less than 20 years	36	19/7
	25-20years	126	68/9
	30-26years	5	2/7
	35-31years	8	4/4
	40-36years	5	2/7
	More than 40 years	3	1/6
Total		183	100

Chart 4.1: Variable chart of subjects' age

4.1.1.3 Education

Table 4-2 shows the educational distribution of the sample members. It can be seen that 68.3% of the respondents have a Bachelor's degree in English (translation and education), 29.5% have a Bachelor's degree in other fields, and 1.1% have a Master's degree. The highest frequency is related to Bachelor's degree in English.

Table 4.2 Education of the respondents

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Lower than Bachelor's degree	2	1/1
Bachelor of English Language (Translation and Education)	125	68/3
Bachelor of other fields	54	29/5
Master of English	2	1/1
Total	183	100

Diagram 4.2: Chart of respondents' education

4.1.1.4 English Language Level

Table 4-3 shows the level of English language of the sample members. It can be seen that 60.7% of the respondents' English language level is average, 29.5% is advanced and 8.9% is weak. These results show that most of the participants in the research have an average level of English.

Table 4.3 English language level of the respondents

Variable		Frequency	Percentage
English language level	Weak	18	9/8
	Average	111	60/7
	Advanced	54	29/5
Total		183	100

Diagram 4.3: English language level chart of the respondents

4.1.1.5 Familiarity with other Languages

Table 4-4 shows familiarity with other languages of the sample members. It can be seen that 36.6% of the respondents are familiar with other languages, but 63.4% of them are only familiar with English.

Table 4.4 Familiarity with other languages of the respondents

Variable		Frequency	Percentage
Familiarity with other languages	Yes	67	36/6
	No	116	63/4
Total		183	100

Diagram 4.4: Chart of respondents' familiarity with other languages

4.2 Checking the Mean of Research Questions

Table 4.5: How the EAP class responds to research questions

Questions	quite agree	agree	no idea	disagree	quite disagree	mean
1. Translanguaging is inherently a natural communication process between bilingual people	% 6/6	%63/7	%27/5	%2/2	0	3/747
2. Translanguaging indicates a deficiency in second language skills	%1/1	%13/2	%24/2	%54/9	%6/6	2/472
3. Using translanguaging in class is considered a suitable and effective language exercise	%4/4	%70/3	%13/2	%12/1	0	3/670
4. Translanguaging is an essential method for learning a new language	%5/5	%58/2	%20/9	%11	%4/4	3/495
5. Using translanguaging has the potential to increase students' self-confidence in English language skills	%12/1	%53/8	%27/5	%5/5	%1/1	3/703
6. Teachers should consider the potential impact of translanguaging when teaching a second language	%11	%70/3	%14/3	%4/4	0	3/879
7. Using translanguaging in the classroom can be especially useful for bilingual students	%12/1	%69/2	%11	%7/7	0	3/851
8. Effective teaching requires a translanguaging to explain and clarify key concepts	%12/1	%62/6	%18/7	%5/5	%1/1	3/803

9. One of the ways to facilitate effective teaching is to use translanguaging for clear and concise guidance	%5/5	%65/9	%26/4	%2/2	0	3/721
10. Expressing feedback through translanguaging creates a powerful mechanism to promote the growth and development of students	%5/5	%49/5	%33	%11	%1/1	3/475
11. Using translanguaging to encourage students' efforts has a positive effect on their motivation and participation	%11	%60/4	%17/6	%11	0	3/721
12. Teachers can make a stronger relationship with their students by using translanguaging	%13/2	%58/2	%19/8	%6/6	%2/2	3/726
13. Translanguaging can be used as a tool to clarify the rules and procedures of the class	%8/8	%53/8	%24	%27/5	%9/9	3/639
14. Using translanguaging in the classroom can be effective especially for less skilled students in English who struggle with	%23/1	%62/6	%11	%1/1	%2/2	3/043
15. In their group activities, students can benefit from translanguaging for engaging discussions around a topic	%11	%51/6	%16/5	%17/6	%3/3	3/377
16. Translanguaging can support students during classroom activities, which increases learning	%12/1	%69/2	%13/2	%4/4	%1/1	3/803
17. Translanguaging improves ideation and other creative activities	%9/9	%42/9	%33	%11	%3/3	3/316
18. Students who use translanguaging to respond to the teacher gain confidence to participate in class discussions	%7/7	%62/6	%18/7	%11	0	3/546
19. Translanguaging can encourage students who are less proficient in English to participate more in class activities	%16/5	%61/5	%17/6	%4/4	0	3/874
20. Asking permission from the teacher during the class using translanguaging, helps students to build more self-confidence	%9/9	%40/7	%29/7	%14/3	%5/5	3/314
21. Translanguaging only includes Persian and English, not other local languages for example: Turkish	%4/4	%15/4	%27/5	%35/2	%17/6	2/480
22. Translanguaging the classroom does not help much in teaching reading skills	%3/3	%30/8	%22	%37/4	%6/6	2/836
23. Translanguaging is only useful for one language skill	%4/4	%17/6	%38/5	%37/4	%2/2	2/786

Among all the research questions, the highest mean score in the EAP class belongs to item number 6 “Teachers should consider the potential impact of translanguaging when teaching a second language” with a score of 3/879 and item number 19 “Translanguaging can encourage students with less English skills to participate more in class activities” with a score of 3/874 and item number 7 “Using translanguaging in class” can be useful for bilingual students with

a score of 3.851. The lowest average score is also for item number 2 “Translanguaging, indicating a deficiency in second language skills” with a score of 2.47 and item number 21 “Translanguaging only includes Persian and English, not other local languages for example: Turkish with a score of 2.408 and item number 23, “translanguaging is only useful for one language skill” 78.2.

Table 4.6: How the EGP class answered the research questions

Questions	Quite agree	agree	No idea	disagree	Quite disagree	mean
1. Translanguaging is inherently a natural communication process between bilingual people	12%	62%	18/5	6/5	6/6	3/717
2. Translanguaging indicates a deficiency in second language skills	3/3	10/9	22/8	50	13	2/413
3. Using translanguaging in class is considered a suitable and effective language exercise	13	52/2	16/3	13	5/4	3/543
4. Translanguaging is an essential method for learning a new language	21/7	40/2	16/3	14/1	7/6	3/543
5. Using translanguaging has the potential to increase students' self-confidence in English language skills	14/1	43/5	27/2	9/8	5/4	3/510
6. Teachers should consider the potential impact of translanguaging when teaching a second language	18/5	51/1	18/5	10/9	1/1	3/750
7. Using translanguaging in the classroom can be especially useful for bilingual students	18/5	45/7	19/6	10/9	5/4	3/608
8. Effective teaching requires a translanguaging to explain and clarify key concepts	26/1	43/5	20/7	5/4	4/3	3/815
9. One of the ways to facilitate effective teaching is to use translanguaging for clear and concise guidance	19/6	50	16/3	8/7	5/4	3/695
10. Expressing feedback through translanguaging creates a powerful mechanism to promote the growth and development of students	8/7	48/9	27/2	12	3/3	3/478
11. Using translanguaging to encourage students' efforts has a positive effect on their motivation and participation	25	44/6	15/2	8/7	6/5	3/728
12. Teachers can make a stronger relationship with their students by using translanguaging	25	44/6	13	12	5/4	3/717
13. Translanguaging can be used as a tool to clarify the rules and procedures of the class	22/8	41/3	20/7	9/8	5/4	3/663
14. Using translanguaging in the classroom can be especially effective for students	39/1	40/2	10/9	6/5	3/3	3/054

who are less proficient in English who are struggling with						
15. In their group activities, students can benefit from translanguaging for engaging discussions around a topic	%12	%38	%21/7	%20/7	%7/6	3/260
16. Translanguaging can support students during classroom activities, which increases learning	%17/4	%55/4	%16/3	%5/4	%5/4	3/739
17. Translanguaging improves ideation and other creative activities	%5/4	%39/1	%30/4	%18/5	%6/5	3/184
18. Students who use translanguaging to answer the teacher, gain confidence to participate in class discussions	%16/3	%43/5	%17/4	%12	%10/9	3/423
19. Translanguaging can encourage students who are less proficient in English to participate more in class activities	%27/2	%50	%9/8	%6/5	%6/5	3/847
20. Asking permission from the teacher during the class using translanguaging helps students to build more self-confidence	%13	%23/9	%25	%19/6	%18/5	2/934
21. Translanguaging only includes Farsi and English, not other local languages for example: Turkish	%7/6	%12	%21/7	%32/6	%26/1	2/423
22. Translanguaging in the classroom does not help much in teaching reading skills	%10/9	%21/7	%19/6	%32/6	%15/2	2/804
23. Translanguaging is only useful for one language skill	%8/7	%12	%39/1	%23/9	%16/3	2/728

Among all the research questions, the highest average score in the EGP class belongs to items number 19, “Translanguaging can encourage students with less proficiency in English to participate more in class activities” with a score of 3.47 and item number 8, “Effective education requires translanguaging to explain and clarify key concepts” with a score of 3.81 and item number 6 “Teachers should consider the potential effect of translanguaging when teaching a second language” with a score of 3.75. The lowest average score is also for item number 2 “translanguaging, indicating a deficiency in second language skills” with a score of 2.41 and item number 21 “translanguaging only includes Persian and English, not other local languages for example: Turkish with a score of 2.42 and item number 23, “translanguaging is only useful for one language skill” with 72.2.

4.3 Checking the Percentage of People Who Agree and Disagree in EAP and EPG Classes

Table 4.7: Checking the percentage of people who agree and disagree

	Classifications	Frequency	Frequency percentage
EAP class	agree	1288	61/53
	disagree	342	16/3
	no idea	463	22/12
EGP class	agree	1183	56/51
	disagree	491	23/45
	no idea	420	20/06

Table 4-7 distribution of the frequency and percentage of the respondents based on the division of the answer. Respondents are divided into three groups: agree, disagree and no idea. Considering the table above, among the EAP class, the highest frequency belongs to the agreeing class with 61%, and among the EGP class, the highest frequency belongs to the agreeing class with 56%. Therefore, in general, it can be said that students' attitude towards translanguaging in EAP class is more favorable; while, the number of disagree is more in the EGP class.

4.4 Calculation of Cronbach's alpha

The value of Cronbach's alpha shows the correlation of the questions of a variable (except for the model). A value of Cronbach's alpha higher than 0.7 indicates acceptable reliability. In Table 4-8, Cronbach's alpha values for EAP and EGP classes are greater than 0.7, indicating acceptable reliability.

Table 4.8: Cronbach's alpha values of two research classes

Description of the group	Number of items	Cronbach's alpha
EAP class	23	0/812
EGP class	23	0/899

4.5 Exploratory Factor Analysis

The factor analysis method can be used as a tool to discover the possible amount of data reduction, which is called exploratory factor analysis. In the present study, exploratory factor analysis is used to group variables that have internal correlation. Often this analysis is done in the early stages of the research. Other goals of exploratory factor analysis are making tool as well as theory. To perform a factor analysis, four main steps are necessary:

- Preparation of a correlation matrix of all the variables used in the analysis and estimation of Communality;
- Extraction of agents;
- Selection and rotation of factors to make the factorial structure simpler and more understandable;
- Interpretation of the results.

5. CONCLUSION

The present study was about the investigation of the attitude of Iranian teachers and students about translanguaging in EAP and EGP classrooms. In this research, in accordance with the topic of the research, a mixed method has been used that includes qualitative and quantitative methods, and four different classrooms (two EGP classes and two EAP classes) have been the subjects of this research. The present research population in the quantitative part includes all female students in undergraduate and master's degree who attend EAP and EGP classes. TEFL students attend two EAP classes and management and architecture students attend two EGP classes. In one of the EAP classes, the focus is on reading and vocabulary skills, and in the

other class, on grammar skills. Four different classrooms (two EGP classes and two EAP classes) are the subjects of this research. Research course was held at Irshad non-profit university of Damavand. Students of this university are selected and registered through entrance exam. All the data of this research were collected during the spring 2023 academic semester. In this research, a library method was used to extract studies and a field method was used to collect statistical data from the studied sample. The data collection tool was a questionnaire in the quantitative part and an interview (semi-structured) tool was used in the qualitative part in order to collect the data.

The method of data collection in the quantitative part was as follows: at first, the questionnaire was distributed online among 123 students in order to determine their attitude towards translanguaging in different ways, which are described in detail in the questionnaire. 60 other students answered the questionnaire in person. Therefore, in total, the questionnaire was distributed among 183 undergraduate and graduate students. In this study, in the qualitative part, four trainers aged 30 to 50 were used to conduct interviews and observations, and to collect data according to the qualitative stage, two types of interview and observation tools were used in the experiment. Four trainers (30 to 50 years old) participated in the interview as part of the research. The general purpose of the interview was to get more information about their views on translanguaging in classrooms and teachers' attitudes towards this phenomenon.

The interview was conducted face-to-face in Persian language to avoid any ambiguity and incorrect answers to the interview questions. In addition, observation was used to better understand the classroom environment. A total of 12 observation sessions were considered for all four classes (three observations for each class) and the training session lasted 90 minutes. In this research, the data obtained from the interview were interpreted in the qualitative section using the inductive method. Based on the answers given during the interview, each person's data was carefully examined and the information was organized in different themes. In addition, the interview data were fully analyzed using thematic analysis method and were categorized into different themes. The questionnaire data was analyzed in the quantitative section using SPSS software and the results were discussed using the interpretation of themes.

It should be noted that in this study, the one sample parametric T-test was used to evaluate students' attitude towards translanguaging in EAP and EGP classes. According to the results obtained from the mentioned test, the average of each class had a significant difference with the assumed average in this study, which is equal to 3. It means that the attitude of the students of that class played a significant role. Therefore, it can be concluded that students' attitudes towards translanguaging in both classes are significant.

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